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Lead Author (Org)	Olivier Rouchon (CNRS)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Esteban Gonzalez Guardia (UPM), Liise Lehtsalu (RDA AISBL), Matti Heikkurinen (CODATA), Anne Sofie Fink (DeiC), Agnes Jasinska (UEDIN, DCC), Simon Hodson (CODATA), Deborah Thorpe (DANS), Liisa Marjamaa-Mankinen (CSC), Bo Nygaard Bai (DeiC)
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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/ Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CDIF	Cross Domain Interoperability Framework
CoP	Community of Practice
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DIF	Domain-specific Interoperability Framework
DoA	Description of Action
DSP	Data Space Protocol
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EC	European Commission
EIF	European Interoperability Framework
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IF	Interoperability Framework
IM	International Model
ISA	Interoperability Solutions for European Public Administrations
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LOST	Legal, Organisational, Semantic and Technical
MSCR	Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry
NIF	National Interoperability Framework
NoS	Network of Stakeholders
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SIMPL	Smart Middleware Platform
SSF	Strategic Stakeholders Forum

Executive Summary

Since the publication of the "Turning FAIR into Reality" report,¹ numerous interoperability frameworks have been developed, each varying in their connection to the European Open Science Cloud Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF), and offering recommendations to improve data accessibility and sharing. In such a diverse and complex ecosystem, researchers, data producers, and service providers may understandably struggle to identify the most suitable framework for their interoperability needs. Hence providing an overview and conducting an analysis on the subject is a timely matter.

This report analyses various interoperability frameworks related to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and beyond. It aims to assess their implementation, challenges, and alignment with global standards to improve data sharing and accessibility across scientific disciplines. It also examines the coordination efforts among EOSC projects, EOSC task forces, and international organisations such as the Research Data Alliance (RDA). The report builds on the outcomes of a series of collaborations and workshops to provide insights into the challenges and advancements in interoperability.

To finally enhance EOSC interoperability, the report recommends establishing a central repository for interoperability guidelines and profiles, as well as developing a crosswalk registry to improve metadata harmonisation. It also advocates for creation of interoperability compliance metrics and a certification framework, as well as alignment with the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model as a strategic benchmark.

The report further suggests that successful implementation of these recommendations will require a sustained engagement with EOSC technical and semantic interoperability initiatives such as the current EOSC Task Forces and continued collaboration with European partnerships such as the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) to further refine interoperability solutions.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.2777/1524>

Introduction

FAIR-IMPACT focuses on the four layers (i.e., legal, organisational, semantic and technical interoperability - aka. LOST) of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF)². The purpose for this deliverable is to build on existing international frameworks and standards in scientific disciplines and on non-scientific large data sources of interest for research, and to foster the alignment between these frameworks.

The EOSC IF is not the only framework available addressing interoperability needs. Since the “Turning FAIR into reality”³ report, many others have been established with various degrees of relationship to the EOSC IF, providing recommendations to enhance data sharing and increase data accessibility. The aim of this deliverable is to evaluate core components and good practices highlighted in these interoperability frameworks from an implementation point of view and to identify challenges or gaps that researchers as data producers, data stewards, or service providers across scientific disciplines could face when adopting them.

For this purpose, collaborations and coordination have been put in place to avoid duplication of efforts and ensure the delivery of a coherent and valuable output, with EOSC-related projects such as EOSC Future,⁴ FAIRCore4EOSC⁵ or EOSC Beyond,⁶ task forces working on EOSC interoperability, and WorldFAIR⁷ as the successful applicant of the HORIZON-WIDERA⁸ call focusing on global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice.

In parallel, stakeholders from outside the current FAIR and EOSC ecosystems have also been engaged: specifically, RDA groups contribute a global perspective on interoperability alignment, and the Data Spaces Support Centre⁹ (where FAIR-IMPACT is involved as an EOSC-project representative) offers a sectorial (private, public) standpoint.

This report will provide a critical analysis of various identified interoperability frameworks, including the ease of deployment of open interfaces, alignments or crosswalks. It will then summarise the findings from a series of recent workshops which were organised to address the challenges identified during the initial study. It will eventually provide recommendations based on the takeaways from the first two phases, to enhance the effectiveness and adoption of the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

² <https://doi.org/10.2777/620649>

³ <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>

⁴ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

⁵ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/>

⁷ <https://worldfair-project.eu/>

⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/widening-participation-and-spreading-excellence_en

⁹ <https://dssc.eu/>

1. Analysis of Interoperability Frameworks

Since the “Turning FAIR into reality” report,¹⁰ a significant number of interoperability frameworks have been established with various degrees of relationship to the EOSC IF, providing recommendations to enhance data accessibility and data sharing.

Figure 1 – The interoperability frameworks ecosystem over time

Researchers, data producers, or service providers could legitimately feel confused when trying to identify the appropriate framework for their interoperability requirements in such a rich, complex ecosystem. The following sub-sections will provide a short history, summary of the context, main recommendations, as well as strengths and limitations of a selection of the most acknowledged, popular existing interoperability frameworks.

1.1 European Interoperability Framework (EIF)

The European Interoperability Framework (EIF)¹¹ was published in 2017 as part of the ISA² programme.¹² The EIF promotes seamless services and data flows for European public administrations to progress the digital single market through a set of recommendations across Europe.

¹⁰ <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.2799/78681>

¹² https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/isa2_en/

The overarching aim of the EIF is to help create a European public service ecosystem where information flows seamlessly across borders to support the digital single market.

The EIF is built upon 12 underlying principles grouped into four categories: context, core, user needs, and cooperation among administrations. It is the EIF that introduces an interoperability model with four layers: legal, organisational, semantic, and technical. The EIF also features a cross-cutting component called "integrated public service governance" and a background layer called "interoperability governance."

The EIF presents base registries as a cornerstone of European public service delivery, defining them as trusted and authoritative sources of information that can be digitally reused. These registries contain fundamental data on items such as people, companies, vehicles, and locations, and are considered the "master data" for public administrations. A key aspect is that a single organisation is responsible for the collection, updating, and preservation of the information, and that this data is of the highest possible quality and integrity. Access to these registries is regulated to comply with privacy and security measures, and they are expected to have data quality assurance plans.

The strengths of the EIF:

- First attempt at addressing the interoperability challenges that arise when data must be readily available for anyone, anywhere.
- Outlines the complexity of the task of delivering interoperability.
- Presents the perspectives of legal, organisational, technical, and semantic interoperability as a way to address the challenge.
- Presents the need for integration of interoperability frameworks at European, national, and thematic level.

The limitations of the EIF:

- The recommendations are on a high conceptual level with limited guidance on how to implement them - and changes accordingly do not seem to have appeared.
- The expectation of the development of national interoperability frameworks and domain-specific interoperability frameworks aligned with the EIF is still missing.
- No specific mention of research and science as a special case.

In conclusion, the EIF is an important introduction to how to approach the interoperability challenge to 'avoid digital fragmentation of services and data, and help the EU's digital single market to work smoothly', but it provides little guidance on implementation. Importantly, the EIF mentions the concept of base registries maintained by public administration in a country, which are defined as trusted and authoritative sources of information that can be digitally reused. These registries contain fundamental data on items such as people, companies, vehicles, and locations, and are considered the "master data" for public administrations. The

challenges of interoperability for base registries are expected to be picked up by the EU Data Spaces.¹³

1.2 EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF)

The EOSC IF was published in 2021 as a report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups on FAIR and Architecture¹⁴. The EIF (described in [section 1.1](#)) has been used as a starting point for the EOSC IF report by structuring it into four layers of interoperability.

The report presents a Reference Architecture Framework (as an extension from the European Interoperability Reference Architecture) in which the emerging EOSC IF can be described and modelled. It contains framework definitions (including relevant terms used and their origins) and abstract building blocks as a tool to group functionality that will be needed to meet the requirements for the EOSC IF.

Following the EIF the EOSC IF is structured into four layers:

- **Technical Interoperability:** This layer deals with applications and infrastructures used to connect systems and services.
- **Semantic Interoperability:** This layer allows the unambiguous exchange of information between systems and services.
- **Organisational Interoperability:** This layer refers to aligning business processes, responsibilities, and expectations between organisations to support common goals.
- **Legal Interoperability:** This layer concerns the use of licenses for shared datasets to avoid conflicts in efforts of combining datasets from multiple sources.. It also applies to regulations or policies under certain conditions.

The report identifies the problems and needs of different scientific communities using a survey¹⁵. As a result of the analysis of the survey, the report provides a set of in total 27 recommendations categorised according to the four layers. As an example, we have provided some of them.

- For Technical Interoperability: i) The use of open specification for EOSC Services, ii) A common security and privacy framework, iii) A clear PID Policy and iv) Easy-to-understand Service-Level Agreements.
- For Semantic Interoperability: i) Associated documentation for semantic artefacts, ii) A clear governance for Semantic Artefacts, iii) Crosswalks to easily discover data and metadata

¹³ <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/semic-support-centre/data-spaces>

¹⁴ <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.2777/620649> (Annex)

- For Organisational Interoperability: i) the definition of interoperability rules to harmonize organizational structures and workflows and ii) clear management of permanent organisation names and functions.
- For Legal Interoperability, i) a clear list of EOSC-recommended licenses and their compatibility with Member States' recommended licenses, ii) the use of human and machine readable licenses, with a centralised source of knowledge and support on copyright and licenses.

Viewpoints presented in the report relay on the work done in the following EOSC Task Forces:

- The architecture building blocks and the structure needed to enable the EOSC Interoperability Framework Semantic and Technical view have been the focus of the EOSC Interoperability Task Force.
- Definition of the Organisational Interoperability building blocks rests on the work done by the EOSC Rules of Participation WG and the EOSC Sustainability WG.
- Definition of the Legal Interoperability building blocks rests on the work done by the Legal team of the Interoperability Task Force.

In 2021, two EOSC Task Forces were created to continue the work started by this report. As a result, they published the following reports in 2023:

- A landscape overview of the EOSC Interoperability Framework - Capabilities and Gaps¹⁶. See the [summary](#) for more information.
- Design Considerations for Technical Interoperability in EOSC¹⁷.
- Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework¹⁸.

As a result, some of the recommendations were reformulated, and a new one was included. We can highlight the following:

- The EOSC Interoperability Guidelines should be recorded in a curated EOSC IF registry/repository.
- Fostering Interoperability with Data Spaces.
- Enabling machine composability via the EOSC Interoperability Framework.
- Align emerging adaptations and implementations to the Semantic View of the EOSC IF reference architecture.

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8399710>

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8109528>

¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10843882>

- Identify and consolidate different approaches to representing and exchanging (meta)data with the FAIR Digital Object model described in the EOSC IF.
- Extend the set of Semantic Business Objects described in the EOSC IF to include artefacts such as mappings and crosswalks.

The strengths of the EOSC IF are:

- It identifies interoperability problems based on a methodology oriented towards scientific communities.
- It provides a theoretical framework to identify the components needed for achieving interoperability, and common definitions for different concepts related to interoperability. It is a good starting point for working on future solutions.

The limitations of the EOSC IF are:

- It is composed of several complex building blocks (components), which makes its implementation and adaptation difficult.
- As a theoretical framework, there is no real implementation of it, and it doesn't provide concrete solutions to specific problems. However, recent developments from FAIR IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC, such as semantic artefact catalogues and data type and mappings repositories, can be integrated in the future.
- Most of the recommendations are too general, making their interpretation by different stakeholders more ambiguous."

1.3 EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework

The EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework was published in 2023¹⁹ as a deliverable of the EOSC Future project²⁰. It presents the overall EOSC Architecture, methodology, tools used for modelling it, visualisations and reference information regarding it. The proposed EOSC reference architecture for the future is designed with extension and evolution through community input in mind.

Regarding the EOSC IF, it highlights that it “aspires to be a framework of policies, guidelines, standards, and best practices that enables different systems, applications, or technologies to communicate and exchange information with each other”. It is intended that a EOSC IF Registry will eventually establish a library of these guidelines, policies etc.

It specifies the implemented governance model of the EOSC IF, including the covering bodies (EOSC Interoperability Advisory Board, EOSC Interoperability Area Chairs, EOSC IF Editorial Board) and their responsibilities. In addition, it also describes the tools (structured EOSC

¹⁹ <https://eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/EOSC-Future-WP3-GEANT-D3.2b-EOSC-Architecture-and-Interoperability-Framework-2023-06-20.pdf>

²⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101017536>

Interoperability Guideline proposal templates for delivery of needed metadata) for the use of external service providers and governance processes for submitting, consulting, and accepting proposed EOSC Interoperability Guidelines (EOSC IGs) to be included in the EOSC IF registry.

It highlights that the technical capability of EOSC IF registry was demonstrated in the beta EOSC Portal and within the EOSC Marketplace for both onboarding and discovery of EOSC IGs. It should be noted that these solutions are not anymore in use for service providers at the time of writing this deliverable.

The EOSC Future project initiated the following Working Groups (WGs) with the focus on collecting requirements and feedback on the technical architecture and interoperability framework to ensure definition of required EOSC IGs, enable common requirements within the EOSC IF, as well as to populate the EOSC IF:

- Compute Continuum Working Group for definition of a metadata schema as an extension of the EOSC Profile in order to better describe the computing resources in the EOSC resource catalogue.
- Science Projects Working Group to steer the overall project technical roadmap and the future enhancement of EOSC architecture based on results of the science projects.
- Research Product Publishing Framework Working Group for definition a research publishing framework to simplify the adoption of that practice, by enabling services of research infrastructures to seamlessly integrate repository deposition workflows in the context of the EOSC.
- Metadata Working Group for improving the 'FAIRness' of community asset metadata in general and especially interoperability and availability of community metadata schema.

In addition, the work of the AAI,²¹ the Semantic Interoperability²² and the Technical Interoperability of Data and Services²³ task forces operating under the EOSC Association, was taken into account by liaising with them. More information about the work of the Technical Interoperability of Data and Services TF can be found in [section 2.1](#) of this report.

The strengths of EOSC Architecture and Interoperability framework are:

- They are built on the recommendations and analysis of the EOSC IF report.
- The modelling of the architecture to which the EOSC IF applies is done both in high-level and in details.

²¹ <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/aai-architecture>

²² <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/semantic-interoperability>

²³ <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/technical-interoperability-data-and-services>

- The EOSC IF Governance model and process are defined, designed and implemented as well as brought up the challenges encountered in implementation of it and the EOSC IF Registry.
- The work of WGs for definition of EOSC IGs interoperability Guidelines for population of EOSC IF has been taken into account.
- Community input for the common requirements from science clusters and science projects was ensured e.g., through collaboration with ENVRI-FAIR²⁴, EOSC-LIFE²⁵, ESCAPE²⁶, PaNOSC²⁷ and SSHOC²⁸ for the Science cases for Development of EOSC Architecture and Frameworks²⁹ deliverable, as well as the first cross-cluster science use case project META-COVID (described in the Appendix G of EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework³⁰) with BBMRI, EU-OPENSOURCE, CESSDA, CLARIN, ECRIN, and EATRIS as representatives of ERICs. More information about the science projects, their impact and innovation is provided in the Compilation of Science Projects Output Information³¹.

The limitations of EOSC Architecture and Interoperability framework are:

- At the time of modeling the architecture, the licence of the tool was limited to the members of the EOSC Future and this caused challenges for sharing the architecture diagrams with the broader community. Currently, there is no information available on how this challenge is tackled.
- The continuation of the EOSC Future work has been somehow unclear for the EOSC community. It is mentioned in the deliverable from the year 2023 that “the relevant parts of the Architecture and Interoperability Framework will be subject to a structured transition to either the EOSC Association, the EOSC operational partner or the EOSC-INFRA2023-01-05 (EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework) and EOSC-INFRA2023-01-04 (Next Generation Services For Operational And Sustainable EOSC Core Infrastructure) consortia, although to which of these is yet to be specified.”
- In October 2024, the EU Commission brought up the value propositions of EOSC EU Node. One of them is that this reference node for EOSC defines the pathway and blueprint (i.e., EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework) for other potential

²⁴ <https://envri.eu/the-envri-fair-project/>

²⁵ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

²⁶ <https://projectescape.eu/>

²⁷ <https://www.panosoc.eu/>

²⁸ <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/project>

²⁹ <https://eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/EOSC-Future-WP3-EMBL-D3.1-Science-Cases-for-Development-of-EOSC-Architecture-and-Framework-2021-09-24.pdf>

³⁰ <https://eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/EOSC-Future-WP3-GEANT-D3.2b-EOSC-Architecture-and-Interoperability-Framework-2023-06-20.pdf>

³¹ https://eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Compilation-of-Science-Project-Outputs-Information_final.pdf

EOSC Node operators to join the federation³². The next steps are still unclear for the larger EOSC community.

1.4 The FDO Framework (FDOF)

The FAIR Digital Object Framework (FDOF) is ‘a framework which defines a model to represent objects in a digital environment and a mechanism to create, maintain and (re)use these objects’.³³ It was published in 2022 following a series of meetings from 2019 onwards that brought together various stakeholders, including the following organisations: RDA, CODATA³⁴, GOFAIR³⁵, US NAS³⁶ and EOSC.

The term FAIR Digital Object (FDO) was first mentioned in the ‘Turning FAIR into reality’ report.³⁷ The report presented a survey and analysis of what is needed to implement FAIR, and it provided a set of concrete recommendations and actions for stakeholders. As such the FDO was foreseen as a fundamental building block for EOSC.

In 2021 the EOSC IF (reference architecture document)³⁸ highlighted the position of FAIR digital objects being at the core of the EOSC interoperability frameworks Semantic View. Based on the FAIR Digital Object concept, the semantic view has been composed of architecture building blocks to describe and model the FDO and functional content on which it is depending. The report contains a proposal for the management of FDOs in the context of EOSC.

At the moment, the understanding and thereby the implementation of FDO as a fundamental semantic object is actively discussed and still undergoing evolution, with the FDO Forum³⁹ playing a significant role in this work.⁴⁰

In summary, the FDO consists of a predictable identifier resolution behaviour, a mechanism to retrieve the object's metadata and an object typing system. Its main goal is to define a set of features to provide foundational support for the FAIR principles.

The strengths of the FDO Framework are:

- ‘The existing global heterogeneity of collection information management and data repositories is pushed down to a level of abstraction such that their design details need to be known only to those who are maintaining those systems.’⁴¹

³² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/open-science-cloud>

³³ <https://fairdigitalobjectframework.org/>

³⁴ <https://codata.org/>

³⁵ <https://www.gofair.foundation/>

³⁶ <https://www.nasonline.org/>

³⁷ <https://doi.org/10.2777/1524>

³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.2777/620649>

³⁹ <https://fairdo.org/>

⁴⁰ <https://council.science/events/codata-fdos-cdif-workshop/>

⁴¹ <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.9.e108808>

- It provides a much needed: ‘layer to overcome the obstacles to data stewardship and standardisation of cross-disciplinary data.’
- It is ‘agnostic to the social and political challenges involved in global integration for facilitating easier research access.’
- It provides support for the digital object's metadata, which has an important role in FAIR⁴², including support for interoperability across FDO's by making data more (machine) accessible, understandable, and usable.

The limitations of the FDO Framework are:

- The FDOF still exists only as a working draft from 2022.
- Aims at a fundamental (technical) level, which it may be challenging to understand at a managerial level to make the decision for adoption.
- The short-term benefits of the adoption of the FDO framework are hard to estimate.
- The implementation of the FDO approach is done on a voluntary/community driven basis within RDA, GOFAIR, and other organisational settings and projects, slowing progress and commitment.

As is pointed out by previous evaluators, there is still work to be done on the FDO: ‘several technical pieces and community practices still need to be developed and further defined, for instance, the FDO type system, how to declare FDO actions, how to resolve persistent identifiers, or how to know which pattern of FDO composition is used’.⁴³ For an EOSC Federation of multiple national, regional, and thematic EOSC nodes⁴⁴ based on already existing services, the value of the FDO approach as a building block has indeed potential. However, broader implementations of the FDO approach to support interoperability remains to be seen.

1.5 Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)

The initial version of the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)⁴⁵ was published in 2024 as a deliverable⁴⁶ of the WP2 of the WorldFAIR⁴⁷ project. It presents a core set of five CDIF profiles which address the most important functions for cross-domain FAIR

⁴² <https://fairdigitalobjectframework.org/>

⁴³ <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1781>

⁴⁴ <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/>

⁴⁵ <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/background/checklistForImplementation.html>

⁴⁶ <https://10.5281/zenodo.11236871>

⁴⁷ <https://worldfair-project.eu/>

implementation. The current point of reference for CDIF and its component profiles is now the “CDIF Book”.⁴⁸

CDIF is not intended to replace existing community standards, but to supplement them for communication across domain and infrastructure boundaries. The CDIF recommendations are based on analysing 11 interoperability case studies to identify common approaches in different scientific areas, communities, and cross-domain challenges. The basic idea is that, to support cross-domain and cross-infrastructure exchange, it is not enough to use domain-specific standards: a set of agreed “domain-neutral” standards for describing data and metadata must be established, to act as a *lingua franca* for these exchanges. Many such standards exist, typically coming from the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) for use on the Web. Similarly, a common approach to technology implementation can be found in the use of JSON-LD as a syntax for expressing these standard modals, with needed metadata embedded in landing pages. This approach is used by many other FAIR approaches and initiatives (i.e., DataCite) as well as by some of the use cases examined (e.g., Oceans InfoHub).

The CDIF divides core interoperability functions into five categories:

- Discovery (discovery and cataloguing of data and metadata resources)
- Data access (specifically, machine-actionable descriptions of access conditions and permitted use)
- Controlled vocabularies (good practices for the publication of controlled vocabularies and semantic artefacts)
- Data integration (description of the structural and semantic aspects of data to make it integration-ready)
- Universals (description of ‘universal’ elements, such as time, geography, and units of measurement)

In each of these categories, the CDIF recommends using specific standards and metadata fields that make achieving cross-domain machine-level interoperability easier, based on common, general-purpose standards. Thus, cross-disciplinary data integration requires only a single set of crosswalks, ontologies and other interoperability mechanisms, instead of bespoke solutions to cover each of the connections in project-specific, bilateral links between data repositories (many-to-many links).

⁴⁸ <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/>

In the EOSC domain, the CDIF categories could be mapped to the functionalities of the federated EOSC ecosystem in the following way:

- Discovery solutions cover metadata approaches that can facilitate integration of EOSC nodes and their resources into the EOSC federation. They can provide the basis for a seamless search for resources across a set of nodes. The CDIF will also provide tools for identifying specific themes and geographical coverage areas of the resources (e.g., to serve specific communities). A published set of crosswalks mapping the CDIF concepts to schema.org⁴⁹, ISO-19115:2014⁵⁰, DCAT⁵¹, DCAT-AP⁵² and FDO Kernel Attributes-2.0⁵³, as well as mapping to RDA Recommendation on PID Kernel Information⁵⁴ and to Signposting relations⁵⁵ can facilitate cross-node resource discovery.
- The Access profile uses Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)⁵⁶ and user-defined actions to convey information about operations that are permitted for holders of EOSC credentials, based on groups they belong to and the policies of the EOSC nodes and resources they want to access.
- Controlled vocabularies that are published and managed in a consistent manner across the EOSC nodes will support resource discovery, authorisation of users (through extensions of the ODRL Actions) across nodes in addition to data validation, and integration in EOSC workflows that use data from several sources. CDIF recommends the use of W3C Simple Knowledge Organization System SKOS⁵⁷ (and the XKIS extension) for describing controlled vocabularies, and the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM) for describing mappings – approaches also seen within many FAIR initiatives and in EOSC.
- Data integration solutions will make cross-resource (and cross-node) workflows more robust by describing the datasets in ways that go beyond the descriptions of the basic syntax (text, binary, etc.). It includes descriptions of variables and their possible values, structural data (“CSV file, headers in the first row,” primary keys), codelists and classifications, mappings between enumerated values (e.g., “professor, administrator,

⁴⁹ <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/metadata/schemaorgimplementation.html>

⁵⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html>

⁵¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/> and <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/metadata/dcat.html>

⁵² <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/semic-support-centre/dcat-ap>

⁵³ <https://zenodo.org/records/7825693>

⁵⁴ <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00031> and <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/metadata/pidkernel.html>

⁵⁵ <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/metadata/signpostinglinkrel.html>

⁵⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/>

assistant” could map to “staff”) and processing descriptions that are used in the interaction (e.g., scripts used for transforming the data).

- Finally, the Universals form a cross-cutting theme across the EOSC data and metadata integration challenge. For any value included in the EOSC resources or resource descriptions, it is important to be able to determine the value space the value belongs to. Currently, CDIF provides recommendations for three specific universals: space, time, and units-of-measurement (UOM).

The initial version of CDIF is intended to be a significant starting point in establishing the information needed to support cross-domain FAIR exchange, but more work remains to be done. The CDIF Working and Advisory groups have been re-organised under the WorldFAIR+ initiative⁵⁸, and will be addressing several additional areas in the coming months:

- FAIR research data and AI: FAIR data can be described using the Croissant ML standard⁵⁹, a subset of the overall CDIF metadata set. By using this approach, the data becomes more useful for the purposes of training and testing LLMs and generative AI models. AI approaches can also be applied in the generation of metadata and other FAIR resources, but essential checks for quality must be performed. CDIF will make recommendations in both these areas, working with the Croissant NL group.
- Large/binary data files: much important research data is held in formats such as NetCDF, HDF5, and Parquet. While these formats have some metadata embedded in them, the metadata is not as open and visible as we might wish. CDIF will make recommendations about how to better describe and disseminate such data files for FAIR reuse.
- Provenance and data context is a complex area, especially given the requirements of cross-domain FAIR. There are many approaches to describing data lineage (PROV), data workflows (Common Workflow Language⁶⁰) and other types of contextualising dependencies (I-ADOPT⁶¹, OGC Observations & Measurements⁶²). These must be used in a coordinated fashion, however, if we are to be able to communicate this critical information to potential users of FAIR resources. CDIF will recommend an approach to doing this.
- Other efforts will include enhancing the ability to automate access to confidential data. The ability to better describe how data integration has been performed (and to make the mappings reusable), and other related topics.

The strengths of CDIF can be summarised as follows:

⁵⁸ <https://codata.org/initiatives/making-data-work/worldfair-2/>

⁵⁹ https://mlcommons.org/2024/03/croissant_metadata_announce/

⁶⁰ <https://www.commonwl.org/>

⁶¹ <https://i-adopt.github.io/>

⁶² <https://www.ogc.org/publications/standard/om/>

- It is based on an analysis of data-sharing practices of several (11) use cases from a wide range of disciplines, as well as observation of good practices internationally. For example, the Discovery profile draws heavily on the ODIS⁶³ and SOSO recommendations⁶⁴.
- The recommendations are based on solutions and standards that are widely used and supported.
- The current five CDIF profiles - Discovery, Data access, Controlled vocabularies, Data integration, and Universals - provide a useful conceptual framework for dividing the overall interoperability challenge into more manageable components. Each profile is accompanied by an implementation guide and worked examples.
- Several ongoing activities are continuing the development of the framework. These include the ongoing work of the CDIF WG, and implementations in a range of projects including CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC and CDIF-4-XAS.
- The utility of DDI-CDI in the CDIF data integration profile has been demonstrated in the WorldFAIR population health case study and in EOSC Future Science Project 9⁶⁵. The UN Statistical Division is working on a DDI-CDI to SDMX mapping to leverage this for SDG indicators.

However, it is important to be aware of the following limitations of CDIF:

- The framework was only recently (Sept-Oct 2024) turned from a monolithic PDF document into a more user-friendly presentation of design principles and implementation guidelines⁶⁶. However, this is still an ongoing process.
- The additional supporting material (detailed implementation guidelines, code samples, training materials...) is not yet consolidated.
- The compliance assessment approach is not yet determined, but is on the development roadmap.
- Tooling is currently limited, but two examples of demonstrator software to provide a CDIF wrapping have been developed.
- The current roadmap for development of additional profiles is extremely ambitious, but is being reinforced by new projects.

1.6 Global Open Research Commons International Model (GORC International Model)

⁶³ <https://odis.org/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.earthcube.org/science-on-schema> and <https://github.com/ESIPFed/science-on-schema.org>

⁶⁵ <https://eoscfuture.eu/data/climate-neutral-and-smart-cities/>

⁶⁶ <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/background/checklistForImplementation.html>

Published in 2023, the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model (IM) describes attributes of Global Open Research Commons.⁶⁷ The model draws on existing good practices, is aspirational (not prescriptive) in nature, and aims to support both the development of individual research commons as well as the work of making research commons interoperable.

The GORC IM is the work of the RDA GORC International Model Working Group⁶⁸, which in turn emerged from the RDA Global Open Research Commons Interest Group.⁶⁹ The Interest Group (IG), founded in 2019, is a global forum for defining what research (data) commons are, for understanding what functionality, coverage, and characteristics such initiatives require, and for coordinating across research commons at global level. The IG considers EOSC as well as the Australian Research Data Commons and the African Open Science Platform as examples of research commons.⁷⁰ The RDA GORC International Model Working Group (WG) launched in 2021 with the aim to identify attributes of commons and to develop a model that developers of commons could use to self-assess and identify development priorities.⁷¹

The GORC IM builds on the GORC IG Typology and Definitions⁷² that describes the typology of the essential elements in a commons. To develop the model, the WG adopted co-creation approaches, organised a speaker series and community workshops, and conducted a literature review.⁷³ This methodology permitted the group to define nine essential elements and break each of those down to a set of categories that provide scope to the broad concepts that the essential elements represent.

Some of the categories are further broken down to subcategories as depicted in the figure⁷⁴ on the side. Each category or subcategory has associated with it one or more attributes, which are “a standard, characteristic, functionality or point of reference about an essential element, category or subcategory from which information can be documented, or measurements or comparisons may be made”; attributes can be further subdivided into sets of features.⁷⁵

⁶⁷ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00099>

⁶⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg/activity/>

⁶⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/global-open-research-commons-ig/activity/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/global-open-research-commons-ig/work-statement/?sow=169802>

⁷¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg/work-statement/?sow=169844>

⁷² <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00087>

⁷³ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00097>, pp. 6-14.

⁷⁴ Extracted from <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00087>

⁷⁵ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00099>, p. 3.

The nine essential elements cover different aspects of research commons, leading to a model that adopts a comprehensive approach and highlights how various elements interact in research commons:

1. Interoperability and standards	<i>Central element at the core of a commons</i>
2. Research objects	<i>Parts of the commons with which users interact</i>
3. Services and tools	
4. Compute, storage, network, AAI [IT infrastructure]	
5. Human capacity	<i>Social/human elements needed to make commons succeed</i>
6. Rules of participation and access	
7. Governance structures	
8. Engagement	
9. Sustainability	

Table 1: The nine essential elements in a commons as outlined in the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model (IM)

‘Interoperability and standards’ is a central element of research commons in the GORC IM, which splits this element into ‘Interoperability’ and ‘Standards & Conventions’, with each sub-element having its own categories, attributes, and features. The model considers interoperability from technical, organisational, and legal perspectives, with technical interoperability divided into issues of syntactic, semantic, and other technical interoperability. The GORC IM explicitly approaches organisational and legal interoperability together with technical interoperability. The GORC IM suggests that while research commons aim to provide access to research objects and services and make these reusable, those commons are also operated by organisations. Because of this, the model invites developers of commons to consider not only their plans and mechanisms for technical interoperability but also plans and mechanisms for organisational and legal interoperability.⁷⁶

The intended target users of the GORC IM are funders, who can use the model to understand and evaluate commons’ structure and evolution, and commons developers, who can use the model to guide their development process, perform internal audits, and assess how their commons fits within a global network of commons infrastructures.⁷⁷

The strengths of the GORC IM are:

- The model was developed by the community and draws on practitioner insights.
- It is aspirational, not prescriptive. This means that users can work with the model in ways that best benefit their own organisation and its needs.

⁷⁶ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00099>, spreadsheet tab “Interoperability”.

⁷⁷ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00097>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14341230>

- It provides target users a comprehensive roadmap that covers all aspects of a research commons, including technical, governance, and policy.
- It includes suggested Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and metrics to measure the performance or evolution and uptake of research commons.
- It invites users to consider technical, organisational, and legal interoperability both within the context of their own research commons as well as in the context of interoperability between research commons.
- It has been adopted at institutional, national, and international level. For example, SURF in the Netherlands have used the GORC IM to drive consortium-internal discussions about the present and the future of the SURF infrastructure as well as to structure discussions about a national EOSC node.⁷⁸ The proposed research commons for Norway (REASON) adopts GORC IM as a reference model.⁷⁹ The draft EOSC Federation Handbook refers to the GORC International Model as a reference model for EOSC Nodes.⁸⁰

The possible limitations of the GORC IM are:

- The model is aspirational and does not prescribe any particular elements or their attributes to developers or funders of commons. For attributes, examples are included but on an equal basis without preference to one approach over another. This, however, is also intentional because the GORC IM developers suggest that not all parts of the model apply to every research commons.
- It is an interoperability framework, but at the level of research commons. It supports the development of interoperable research commons and considers interoperability in (and between) research commons in terms of technical (syntactic and semantic), operational, and legal interoperability. GORC IM neither approaches research object level interoperability nor provides concrete solutions.

1.7 Data Spaces Support Centre Blueprint

The Blueprint was released in 2023 as a deliverable⁸¹ of the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) project⁸² and has been revised three times since then. It consists of a comprehensive set of guidelines to support the development cycle of the Common European Data Spaces.⁸³ At the end of 2023, the DSSC has consolidated the contributions from the Data Spaces

⁷⁸ https://archive.rd-alliance.org/system/files/documents/Adoption_GORC_SURF.pdf

⁷⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10410202>

⁸⁰ The draft EOSC Federation Handbook was shared with EOSC Winter School 2025 participants on January 16, 2025. Reference to GORC is included in Chapter 5, which describes scientific services and resources integrated in EOSC Federation via EOSC Nodes and the requirements for their integration.

⁸¹ <https://dssc.eu/space/BPE/179175433/Data+Spaces+Blueprint+%7C+Version+0.5+%7C+September+2023>

⁸² <https://dssc.eu/>

⁸³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

community in the Recommendations for the Future Roadmap for Data Spaces regarding interoperability.⁸⁴

As the previous versions, the new Blueprint 1.5,⁸⁵ published in late 2024, includes a common glossary in use, a conceptual model of a data space, data space building blocks, recommended standards and specifications as well as the description of a co-creation method.

According to the glossary, a Data Space is an interoperable framework, based on common governance principles, standards, practices and enabling services, that enables trusted data transactions between participants. Definitions regarding interoperability are included, as outlined in Table 2 below:

Term	Description
Data space interoperability	The ability of participants to seamlessly exchange and use data within a data space or between two or more data spaces.
Intra-data space interoperability	The ability of participants to seamlessly access and/or exchange data within a data space. Intra-data space interoperability addresses the governance, business and technical frameworks (including the data space protocol and the data models) for individual data space instances.
Cross-data space interoperability	The ability of participants to seamlessly access and/or exchange data across two or more data spaces. Cross-data spaces interoperability addresses the governance, business and technical frameworks to interconnect multiple data space instances seamlessly.

Table 2: Definitions of interoperability as outlined in the Data Spaces Support Centre Blueprint

The Technical Building Blocks section of the Blueprint identifies the technical capabilities that are needed to implement data spaces and provides standard specifications for each of them. This allows data space governance authorities and participants to make technical choices in an informed way. It consists of several areas of focus, among which is data interoperability. Data interoperability here includes:

- Data Models: capabilities to define and use shared semantics in a data space.
- Data Exchange: capabilities relating to the actual exchange and sharing of data.
- Provenance & Traceability: capabilities for tracking the data sharing process so it becomes traceable and can be checked for compliance purposes.

⁸⁴<https://dssc.eu/space/News/blog/223379465/Recommendations+for+the+FUTURE+ROADMAP+FOR+DATA+SPACES>

⁸⁵<https://dssc.eu/space/bv15e/766061169/Data+Spaces+Blueprint+v1.5+-+Home>

The suggested standards can be found in the data models specifications, and include DCAT⁸⁶ for the semantic description of catalogues of data and services, SKOS⁸⁷ for vocabularies, and OWL⁸⁸ ontologies.

Alongside the Blueprint, the technical interoperability is supported by the Data Space Protocol (DSP)⁸⁹, which defines a standardised set of specifications for data sharing.

The strengths of the DSSC Blueprint are:

- The Blueprint provides common standards and guidelines to ensure seamless data exchange across different sectors and ecosystems, that align with the EOSC Interoperability Framework (DCAT, ODRL, etc.).
- It is designed to support both small-scale pilots and large-scale implementations, making it adaptable for different use cases, and enables different implementations and customisations while maintaining a core set of interoperability principles.
- It ensures alignment with EU regulations like GDPR,⁹⁰ the Data Act,⁹¹ and the Digital Markets Act,⁹² helping organisations navigate legal challenges.
- It includes a co-creation method with questions to express the data space project needs and make informed decisions to implement the building blocks.

The limitations of the DSSC Blueprint are:

- The Blueprint is still a work in progress. Version 2.0 is due to be released in spring 2025. Many aspects are still evolving, which may create uncertainty in long-term adoption.
- The data interoperability is one pillar on the technical side, but is diluted with the other business and organisational building blocks. The Blueprint involves multiple technical, legal, and governance layers, which can be challenging for organisations with limited expertise.
- The adoption by data spaces and data space initiatives proceeds slowly, as some of them had started their work before the launch of DSSC. Organisations may hesitate to adopt DSSC-based specifications if they already rely on proprietary or cloud-based solutions that offer similar data-sharing capabilities.

⁸⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

⁸⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/>

⁸⁸ <https://www.w3.org/OWL/>

⁸⁹ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/dataspace-protocol>

⁹⁰ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

⁹¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-act>

⁹² https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/digital-markets-act-ensuring-fair-and-open-digital-markets_en

- Even if the DSSC has put together Thematic Groups as forums to foster knowledge sharing and co-learning among the DSSC stakeholders engaged in data space developments, the Blueprint lacks available stories of successful implementations. See the [Contribution to Data Spaces Support Centre Thematic Groups](#) section for more information.

2. Takeaways from Collaborations and Workshops

2.1 Landscape Overview of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) Capabilities and Gaps

In 2023, the EOSC Technical Interoperability of Data and Services Task Force published a landscape overview of the EOSC Interoperability Framework Capabilities and Gaps⁹³. The document presents the foundations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF), the EOSC Architecture, and the Minimum Viable EOSC, as they have been defined by the EOSC Working Groups, established during the previous EOSC Governance, and describes their evolution under EOSC Future, other relevant EOSC projects, and via the different task forces of the EOSC Association

In the report it is reminded that the key objective of the EOSC IF is to integrate in a homogenous framework all the past, current and future work on interoperability in the European Research Area. The report provides information about ongoing EOSC initiatives on interoperability at the time.

The task force reports the results of an EOSC IF gap analysis from the viewpoints of EOSC IF Architecture components and the overall data and service interoperability and provides a list of recommendations to achieve full interoperability in EOSC.

The main recommendations provided in the report are outlined in Table 3 below:

Area	Recommendations
Establishment of the EOSC Interoperability Framework	The EOSC IF has to be established adopting a bottom-up approach aiming to put together, in a unique framework, the results of the most relevant initiatives that are working on interoperability in the ERA, such as general-purpose e-Infrastructures (EGI, EUDAT, GEANT, OpenAIRE), thematic clusters and other scientific communities, as well as through global and cross-domain initiatives like the Research Data Alliance, AARC/AEGIS, GO-FAIR and CODATA
Establishment of the EOSC Interoperability Framework	The EOSC IF should embed a library of Interoperability Guidelines (EOSC IGs) into the EOSC IF registry to promote the branding and adoption of standards and common best practices in EOSC. The EOSC IGs should specify the APIs, the metadata format of the exchanged data (the EOSC Profiles ⁹⁴) and all the processes required to really make two resources interoperable. The EOSC IF should include EOSC IGs for EOSC Core and EOSC Exchange (horizontal and thematic) services.
Implementation of the EOSC Interoperability Framework	The EOSC IGs should be recorded in a curated EOSC IF registry/repository (which stores and manages the library of IGs). A common metadata structure should be adopted to describe IGs, this will make information on interoperability best practices available in a homogeneous way facilitating the discovery, sharing and reuse.

⁹³ <https://zenodo.org/records/8399710>

⁹⁴ <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-providers-hub/what-are-eosc-profiles>

Implementation of the EOSC Interoperability Framework	The EOSC Resource Catalogue (which allows viewing of EOSC resources) should gather information about EOSC IGs from the EOSC IF Registry and annotate resource descriptions with the guidelines they comply with. This mechanism enables an interoperability-driven overlay of EOSC resources across different disciplines and the discovery of resources based on interoperability features.
Enabling machine composability via the EOSC Interoperability Framework	Machine composability requires that EOSC IGs are annotated with configuration templates, structured metadata profiles through which providers can describe the actual access parameters of their services for a given guideline. In such a way, a provider can declare the actual parameters to access a given interface of its service together with the compatibility with a certain IG.
Enabling data interoperability via the EOSC Interoperability Framework	The EOSC IF will also include IGs for Data interoperability . These IGs should ensure that datasets can be exchanged between systems such that datasets can be understood, combined, processed and analysed by various EOSC services. This requires data to be machine-readable and available in suitable forms with enough contextual information to be interpretable and meaningfully composed with other data.
Interoperability with Data Spaces	EOSC initiatives (EOSC-A, EOSC related projects, etc.) have to coordinate with the Data Space Support Centre (DSSC) , and through the DSSC with other Data Spaces, to ensure that such interoperation is possible through the technical, governance, access and use, and semantic interoperability mechanisms that EOSC will implement.
Interoperability with Data Spaces	EOSC initiatives should join the SIMPL open source community to work with the SIMPL project through a co-design approach to ensure that the development of SIMPL takes into account the experiences in interoperability of EOSC and to ensure the interoperability of the Data Spaces with EOSC and vice versa.
Interoperability with EuroHPC ^{95 96}	It may be necessary to develop gateways to ensure the interconnection between world-class supercomputing systems from EuroHPC and EOSC services to serve research communities leveraging both infrastructures.

Table 3: Main recommendations from the landscape overview in the EOSC Interoperability Framework Capabilities and Gaps report

The report highlights that the EOSC Future project has been the first initiative that delivered an overall design and a first implementation of EOSC IF. After the end of EOSC Future, the EOSC IF will be delivered by the EOSC Platform operators (referred also in the 2023 second version of the EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework delivered by the EOSC Future project).

Two of these recommendations directly concern interoperability with data spaces:

- Need for coordination between EOSC projects and DSSC.

⁹⁵ https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/index_en

⁹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RZn2hRJo5Zs>

- Need to get involved with SIMPL⁹⁷, an open source, secure middleware platform that supports data access and interoperability in European data initiatives, to ensure that this project facilitates interoperability between the Common European Data Spaces and EOSC.

To ensure interoperability and facilitate the management of its various components, the DSSC has adopted the concept of building blocks⁹⁸, organised in two categories:

- Organisational and Business Building Blocks
- Technical Building Blocks

These building blocks can be associated with the three thematic groups detailed in the next [section](#).

2.2 Contribution to the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) Thematic Groups

The dialogue and collaboration between FAIR-IMPACT and the DSSC have continued, to foster alignments between the Common European Data Spaces, among which the EOSC is seen as the Research Data Space. FAIR-IMPACT, as a selected EOSC-related project along with EOSC Focus and EOSC-Future, has been invited to participate in this initiative to provide feedback based on EOSC experience, and contribute to the DSSC Governance, Business and Technology thematic groups via three project partners (CNRS, RDA, CODATA) that have attended meetings since the DSSC kick-off and over the duration of the project.

The DSSC thematic groups are putting together building blocks to enable the deployment and interoperability between the Common European Data Spaces. They are not new communities, but ways to organise existing communities and NoS around topics and themes.

Their main objective is to share and co-create knowledge, in between the CoP, the SSF and other stakeholders. The scope is wide and covers a large set of topics and interrelationships between them. The participation in the groups is voluntary, and doesn't bring explicit obligations for participants. Organisations part of the NoS will assign participants to the thematic groups. There is no selection process. The criteria is to belong to CoP, SSF, or collaborations/liaisons.

2.2.1 The Business Thematic Group

The “Business of Data Spaces” Thematic Group brings together experts, professionals, and researchers interested in business challenges in Data Spaces with the main objective of sharing best practices and identifying new knowledge.

⁹⁷ <https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu/>

⁹⁸ <https://dssc.eu/space/BBE/178421761/Building+Blocks+%7C+Version+0.5+%7C+September+2023>

The group investigates ideas to feed the Blueprint building blocks for business at different levels. The focus is twofold: develop business case patterns and stages of development to answer questions of why data space should exist and generally why people should join, and design strategies for building a business plan with realistic stakeholder/customer engagement, willingness to pay and value measurement, etc. This is very relevant for FAIR-IMPACT as the EOSC business model is still in development, with different stakeholder interests as it involves research institutions, national governments, EU bodies, private sector, and cloud service providers, each with different goals and funding expectations. Thus, having examples of successful implementations from other data spaces from the public or private sectors proved to be a valuable takeaway.

2.2.2 The Governance Thematic Group

The “Governance of Data Spaces” Thematic Group is composed of experts, professionals, and researchers interested in governance and legal challenges in Data Spaces with the primary goal of sharing knowledge, and co-creating new knowledge.

A major task of a Data Space initiative is to develop a governance framework that contains the rules and practices for the data space's governance, management, and operations: the set of principles, standards, policies (rules/regulations), and practices that apply to the governance, management, and operations within a particular scope (e.g., a data space, a data space initiative, or data spaces blueprint) as well as to the enforcement thereof, and the resolution of any conflicts.

A webinar titled "Governance for Data Spaces"⁹⁹ held on June 26, 2023, emphasised the critical role of robust governance frameworks in ensuring secure and efficient data sharing. The session highlighted that clear governance structures are essential for establishing trust among participants and ensuring compliance with relevant regulations.

2.2.3 The Technology Thematic Group

The “Technology of Data Spaces” Thematic Group consists of experts, professionals, and researchers interested in technology and technical challenges in data spaces with the main objective to share knowledge and best practices, as well as co-create new knowledge. As a synergy amongst Data Spaces, it carries out a comparison among interoperability frameworks to propose a high level architecture approach (centralised, distributed, hybrid) and contributes to the integration of Blueprint building blocks into existing data systems to enhance a system of systems (interoperability among data spaces).

The contribution of FAIR-IMPACT has been to promote the FAIR principles, raise awareness on the EOSC governance model and rules of participation, and ensure alignment of the DSSC deliverables (e.g., the Blueprint) with the interoperability frameworks of the EOSC ecosystem. As an example, the FAIR principles, metrics and tools for auto assessment were presented during a DSSC Technology WG meeting in June 2024 by a representative from FAIR-IMPACT.

⁹⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cQ95qHn1UBw>

The EOSC federation mechanisms were also presented by an EOSC Beyond partner in September 2024.

2.3 FAIR-IMPACT Workshops

Several workshops have been organised during the second half of the FAIR-IMPACT project. Significant stakeholders from EOSC Projects and beyond have been invited to debate the development of the EOSC ecosystem with focus on all four interoperability perspectives. The plan was to place the workshops interlinked with events like the EOSC Symposium 2024, the FAIR-IMPACT All Hands meeting and the RDA 23rd plenary. These workshops gave an opportunity to define the scope of the work, exchange views and practices, and validate the findings exposed in this report.

2.3.1 FAIR-IMPACT All-Hands Meeting 2023

During the EOSC Symposium 2023 in Madrid, project partners with the responsibility of exploring interoperability aspects with the EOSC and FAIR ecosystems actively participated in the sessions about the Data Spaces. Following this interaction, the same group of partners used the opportunity of the FAIR-IMPACT All-Hands Meeting 2023 to consolidate information on recent developments and define specific activities with regards to LOST interoperability, and more specifically the aspects pertaining to interoperability with the EOSC ecosystem, in line with the project's plan of action.

This event can be seen as the real kick-off of the project work, as these discussions influenced the direction of relevant activities to be conducted within the task, but also defined interactions and set a clear timeline for coordination with other EOSC-related projects working in the realm of interoperability, as well as the Common European Data Spaces.

2.3.2 Co-located FAIR-IMPACT Workshop at RDA Plenary #23 2024

This invitation-only workshop was co-located with the RDA 23rd Plenary in San José, Costa Rica on 11 November, 2024.¹⁰⁰ The objective of the workshop titled “Interoperability Frameworks in a Global Perspective”, was to have a discussion about interoperability in research commons by bringing together participants with the experience of developing and/or supporting the development of research commons across the globe.

The workshop included the presentations detailed in [Appendix](#). The discussion between the presenters and workshop participants highlighted a number of challenges to interoperability in the context of research commons:

1. The sheer number of interoperability frameworks available for reference can be daunting when developing a research commons. Practical methods to filter and apply relevant guidelines are needed;

¹⁰⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/interoperability-frameworks-global-perspective-fair-impact-co-located>

2. Many interoperability efforts rely on project-based funding, which raises concerns about long-term viability of frameworks, guidelines, tools, and services;
3. Achieving interoperability requires cross-sector collaboration and flexible solutions tailored to diverse needs; technical, semantic, organisational, and legal interoperability needs must be balanced;
4. Participants also emphasised the importance of training and cultural shifts to build shared understanding around data sharing and management.

Going forward, as key takeaways, the workshop participants called for real-world implementation stories that would provide practitioners with a roadmap for adopting interoperability frameworks, more robust funding models and governance structures to ensure sustainability of interoperability frameworks, and training programmes to enable researchers, particularly early-career researchers, to engage with FAIR principles and implement FAIR in their local communities.¹⁰¹

2.3.3 EOSC Focus Workshop on Data Spaces 2024

This workshop was held on invitation only in TU Wien in December 2024, with the objective to exchange knowledge, experiences, and current status between different players regarding three main topics which had been selected prior to the meeting:

1. Data sharing, protection and security mechanisms;
2. Technical infrastructure/interoperability and integration;
3. Artificial Intelligence to support FAIR data/data quality.

It also aimed at looking for potential synergies between EOSC, the relevant Data Spaces and DSSC, and increasing the visibility of EOSC as a transversal Data Space. The participants and topics are listed in [Appendix](#).

The main takeaways from the “technical infrastructure/Interoperability and integration” brainstorming session:

- Cross-domain interoperability;
 - A challenge is how to mature secure domain-based interactions (community-based approaches);
 - To address this, there is a need to stimulate “interfacing”.
- Attracting users/stimulating data sharing
 - The value proposition for this needs to be very well specified;

¹⁰¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/from-frameworks-to-action-lessons-from-the-fair-impact-co-located-workshop-at-the-rda-plenary/>

- The vehicle to do so may be to enhance data visibility - otherwise, need to think about how to attract people to the resources.
- Governance and policies
 - There are very many different models and notions;
 - Handling of sensitive data is a particular aspect/challenge;
 - There may be challenges in funding thematic providers/RIs to the level needed.
- FAIR practices need to be enhanced in the appropriate way
 - Provenance, DOIs;
 - Long-term availability of data.
- Recognition of technical development

This work will ultimately feed a progress report (due March 2025), which will be a follow-up to the EOSC Technical Collaboration with other European Partnerships and relevant initiatives deliverable.¹⁰²

2.3.4 FAIR-IMPACT Final Workshop 2025 (Co-located with EOSC Winter School 2025)

The final FAIR-IMPACT workshop¹⁰³ aimed at continuing the EOSC interoperability discussions based on the conclusions of the co-located event in the RDA 23rd Plenary 2024 ([section 2.3.2](#)). The workshop was organised as an EOSC Winter School pre-event and had three main goals:

- Maximising the utility of the previous workshop results in the EOSC context.
- Collecting and showcasing real-world implementation stories that can provide a roadmap for adopting EOSC interoperability solutions.
- Finding practical methods to select and apply relevant guidelines by:
 - Identifying themes and topics for further discussion during the EOSC Winter School, and
 - Prepare a summary and recommendations for workshop participants' consultation after the EOSC Winter School.

The above three goals were reflected in the structure of the workshop: a concise “setting the stage” to cover the state of play of the EOSC interoperability and a recap of the results of the

¹⁰² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10893958>

¹⁰³ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-impact-announces-co-located-final-interoperability-workshop-eosc>

previous workshops, followed by two in-depth interoperability case studies and five “lightning talks”, ending with a discussion and brainstorming about the next steps.

The workshop kicked off with a presentation by Javier Lopez Albecete (European Commission) reflecting on the inherent challenges and trade-offs when building interoperability across a large group of heterogeneous communities. The role of the GORC model (presented in section 1.6) as a strategic planning tool that supports alignment with international efforts, was highlighted. Next, Olivier Rouchon (CNRS-DDOR) summarised the previous workshop results and presented the “LOST” categorisation of interoperability that covers Legal, Organisational, Semantic, and Technical interoperability.

The topics and speakers of the interoperability success stories presented in the next part of the workshop are listed in [Appendix](#). These presentations served as starting points for lively discussion on different aspects of interoperability, leading to valuable insights that have been incorporated into the recommendations ([chapter 3](#)).

The following common themes emerged:

- Trade-offs between inclusivity and efficiency and between community-driven and top-down approaches: How to best converge on a minimum set of standards? Do we lose domain-specific information when adopting more general standards? Some decisions need to be made in a top-down manner (e.g., standards enable both collaboration and innovation), but especially in the initial stages of adoption, it may be necessary to find a common ground in order to “agree to disagree”.
- The interplay between the interoperability layers: The success of semantic or technical interoperability frameworks depends on whether they are supported by or aligned with organisational/legal interoperability frameworks and constraints.
- Any interoperability framework requires sustained efforts that are beyond the lifetimes of individual projects. RDA working and interest groups play a crucial role in this, together with sustained research infrastructures (such as ELIXIR¹⁰⁴) and groupings that bring together multiple initiatives (such as WorldFAIR+).

The wrap-up part of the workshop yielded several tentative consensus conclusions. First, the participants agreed that “interoperability” is not a boolean measure but a continuum across all of the legal, organisational, semantic, and technical layers. This complexity should be captured and expressed through metrics to be developed in the follow-up activities.

Similarly, the cost-benefit analysis tools to support decision-making related to some of the trade-offs identified by the participants would lower the cost of achieving practical interoperability, especially in cross-disciplinary settings. The workshop also identified both technical and governance gaps: specifically, interoperability protocols need more attention on the technical level, while clarifying the governance model used to determine if a solution

¹⁰⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/>

or service is “EOSC-compliant” or “EOSC-approved” would support a more efficient selection and implementation of EOSC-related interoperability solutions.

3. Recommendations

The following recommendations aim to enhance the effectiveness and adoption of the EOSC Interoperability Framework by addressing key challenges and opportunities identified in the [frameworks analysis](#) as well as the takeaways from the different [collaborations and workshops](#). These recommendations focus on improving the ease of the implementation of legal, organisational, semantic, and technical interoperability within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. They are for concrete actions, or initiatives, and ready to be picked up by other projects or in funding programmes.

Recommendation #1: Profiles and guidelines repository

The EOSC IF has now been integrated in the new EOSC Federation Handbook,¹⁰⁵ which focuses on technical interoperability for services (EOSC nodes, service providers, etc.). Interoperability for resources and datasets still needs to be addressed, and the stakeholders (researchers, data producers, data stewards, resource providers) need concrete examples of successful implementations within their communities to be able to identify which ones fit their needs.

The different workshops organised have demonstrated that a central repository for interoperability guidelines tailored for these different stakeholders is desired. A proof of concept of an EOSC IF registry has been delivered as part of the EOSC Future project. The EOSC Beyond project could take it further and extend its initial capabilities to include resources like datasets. Such a repository could consist of a catalogue of interoperability profiles organised into structured categories reflecting communities and mapping registries describing cross-walks between the profiles, facilitating the stakeholders journey: from the initial source of interest (use case), through a discovery path (how to find EOSC solutions without any background on EOSC), until the monitoring of resources usage and reliability.

Recommendation #2: Mappings and crosswalks registry to support reuse and adoption across domains

Crosswalks and mappings are key components in supporting cross-domain interoperability because they allow concepts from different domains to be related, facilitating their alignment. To avoid an excessive number of them and to ensure their findability, they must be registered in a registry with appropriate documentation and persistent identifiers (PIDs). Tools such as MSCR¹⁰⁶ in combination with DTR¹⁰⁷ can be used to create and to register these mappings, as well as to create PIDs.

Semantic artefacts are used to add meaning to metadata and data fields. These artefacts can vary across different domains, making cross-domain communication challenging. A catalogued semantic artefact repository can help address this issue by making artefacts accessible to researchers from other communities, reducing the number of redundant

¹⁰⁵ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/>

¹⁰⁶ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

¹⁰⁷ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-data-type-registry-dtr>

semantic artefacts and crosswalks. A survey of semantic artefacts can be found at Zenodo¹⁰⁸, while an example of a semantic artefact catalogue, together with a methodology is described in the context of the FAIR-IMPACT project.¹⁰⁹

Recommendation #3: Clear governance of EOSC adopted interoperability frameworks, models and solutions

The structure of EOSC is still evolving. We already see a high number of interoperability frameworks, models, and solutions, but also these are still evolving. The [FAIR-IMPACT workshops](#) highlighted that this dynamic environment creates uncertainty about decision-making, responsibilities, and long-term sustainability of existing and in-development interoperability frameworks, models, and solutions. Actors in this environment need clarity about who has the mandate to declare interoperability frameworks EOSC compliant and ready to be adopted in the EOSC ecosystem, who is responsible for the governance and sustainability of EOSC-compliant interoperability frameworks and related guidelines, how do actors in this environment propose new interoperability approaches to meet domain-specific gaps or missed requirements, and how such new and in-development approaches interact with previously adopted ones.

Recommendation #4: Clear guidance to adopters about available interoperability frameworks, models, and solutions and their implementation

The [FAIR-IMPACT workshops](#) highlighted that the sheer number of interoperability frameworks, models, and solutions can be overwhelming for adopters and users.¹¹⁰ Adopters and users ask for tools (e.g. the repository mentioned in Recommendation #1) to navigate the frameworks, models, and solutions and guidance on identifying those frameworks, models, or solutions that are relevant to their use cases. Adopters and users also need roadmaps that support the implementation of the identified frameworks, models, and solutions in their systems and workflows. When alternative approaches for cross-domain interoperability are available, the roadmaps should include cost-benefit assessments to help adopters choose the optimal approach. For example, approaches such as standardised metadata based on higher abstraction level concepts will lead to a loss of some information but will require less effort than mappings. Similarly, a rapid standardisation (or *de facto* standardisation) in cross-domain use case may incur the risk of lower participation of the communities involved, but can lead to faster development of showcases and spearhead activities that efficiently build momentum for broader deployment.

Recommendation #5: Adopt existing community-based interoperability frameworks, models, and solutions that support a holistic approach to interoperability

¹⁰⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12799796>

¹⁰⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12579779>

¹¹⁰ The Interoperability in EOSC sessions (joint sessions between EOSC Task Forces 1 and 3 and Opportunity Area Expert Group 2) at the EOSC Winter School 2025 also captured over 140 individual interoperability solutions in one 30-minute exercise. See slides: https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/2.-SP1-Reporting-Session_21-Jan-2025-17-18_00.pdf

Our [Analysis of Interoperability Frameworks](#) as well as the [FAIR-IMPACT workshops](#) identified a number of community-based interoperability frameworks, models and solutions that support interoperability at various levels (e.g. interoperability between Nodes, interoperability of research objects cross domains, interoperability of research objects within a domain) as well as the various aspects of interoperability (i.e. legal, organisational, semantic, technical (LOST) interoperability).

We recommend that existing, community-based solutions that support a holistic approach to interoperability (LOST) are adopted whenever possible. The adoption of existing, community-based solutions helps to reduce the risk of information overload among adopters and users and the existing solutions already provide a basis for a coherent, commonly agreed reference material to achieve a holistic approach to interoperability. The existing, community-based frameworks, models, and solutions include e.g. [GORC International Model](#) and [Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework \(CDIF\)](#) outlined above. Both the GORC International Model and CDIF approach a multitude of interoperability-related challenges and offer adopters and users a clear roadmap (GORC International Model) and a cross-domain solution (CDIF) that are developed in reference to existing best practice.

#	For whom?	Recommendations
#1	Service provider and researchers	Interoperability profiles and guidelines tailored for these different stakeholders should be gathered in a central repository
#2	Service provider and researchers	Mappings and crosswalks registry to support reuse and adoption across domains.
#3	Policy makers, funders	Clear governance of EOSC adopted interoperability frameworks, models and solutions
#4	Policy makers, funders, service providers	Clear guidance to adopters about available interoperability frameworks, models and solutions and their implementation
#5	Policy makers, funders, service providers	Adopt existing community-based interoperability frameworks, models and solutions that support a holistic approach to interoperability

■ Table 4: Cross-domain recommendations for the EOSC IF

4. Conclusions and next steps

The landscape of interoperability continues to evolve, with multiple frameworks contributing to legal, organisational, semantic, and technical (LOST) interoperability. However, challenges remain in terms of framework adoption, practical implementation, and long-term sustainability.

These should be addressed by sustaining further engagement with technical and semantic interoperability initiatives such as the EOSC Task Forces, other EOSC-related projects like EOSC Beyond (for the repository of interoperability guidelines) and FAIRCORE4EOSC (for the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry¹¹¹) or global organisations and initiatives including the RDA FAIR Mappings WG,¹¹² and continued collaboration with European partnerships such as the Data Spaces Support Centre to refine interoperability solutions.

One of the difficulties identified in the relevant FAIR-IMPACT work on technical and semantic interoperability is adapting the recommendations to specific actions due to the occasional use of ambiguous language. One of the objectives of this task is to refine the recommendations into specific indicators that can potentially be evaluated in the future to assess compliance with a specific interoperability policy. These indicators have been identified by the project, and presented in various forums such as the synchronisation workshops.¹¹³ An example of them, and their application to FAIRCORE4EOSC components, can be found in this report published by the project FAIR IMPACT.¹¹⁴

Findings in this deliverable will be promoted in the working groups where authors are members such as the Metadata, Ontologies and Interoperability - Opportunity Area Expert Group¹¹⁵ and the EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability Interoperability TF.¹¹⁶

¹¹¹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

¹¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-mappings-wg/>

¹¹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14848907>

¹¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10940164>

¹¹⁵ <https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa2-metadata-ontologies-and-interoperability/>

¹¹⁶ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/technical-and-semantic-interoperability-task-force/>

5.2 Appendix

5.1 Participants to the Data Spaces Support Centre Thematic Groups

Participants	Topic
Eight meetings were organised from May 2023 to April 2024, with two FAIR-IMPACT partners: CNRS, RDA.	Business Thematic Group
Six sessions were held from May 2023 to January 2024, with two FAIR-IMPACT partners: CNRS, RDA.	Governance thematic Group
The meetings are scheduled on a monthly basis, nineteen sessions have been organised from May 2023 to November 2024, with three FAIR-IMPACT partners: CNRS, RDA, CODATA.	Technology thematic Group

5.3 Participants and topics of the Workshops

5.3.1 Participants/speakers and topics of the FAIR-IMPACT All-Hands meeting in 2023

Participants/Speakers	Topic
Olivier Rouchon (CNRS), Ingrid Dillo (DANS), Josefine Nordling (CSC), Liisa Marjamaa-Mankinen (CSC), Joy Davidson (UEDIN/DCC)	FAIR-IMPACT, EOSC Interoperability Framework
Chris de Loof (Belnet)	EOSC Focus
Mark Dietrich (EGI)	EOSC Future
Savvas Rogotis (DSSC)	Data Spaces Support Centre

5.3.2 Speakers and topics at the FAIR-IMPACT Workshop at RDA Plenary #23 2024

Participants/Speakers	Topic
Olivier Rouchon (CNRS)	FAIR-IMPACT and interoperability frameworks in the context of EOSC
CJ Woodford and Mikiko Tanifuji (RDA GORC International Model WG)	GORC International Model
Yann Le Franc (eScience Data Factory)	Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)
Keith Russell (ARDC)	Thematic research data commons in Australia

CJ Woodford (Digital Research Alliance of Canada)	Digital Research Alliance of Canada's efforts to align with GORC IM to achieve interoperability
Vaida Plankyte (ResearchSpace)	REASON (a proposed Norwegian research commons)

5.3.3 Participants/speakers and topics at the EOSC Focus Workshop on Data Spaces 2024

Participants/Speakers	Topic
Olivier Rouchon (CNRS)	FAIR-IMPACT
Sara Garavelli (CSC)	EOSC Data Space
Franciska de Jong (CLARIN)	Language Data Space
Ines Vodopivec (Europeana)	Cultural Heritage Data Space
Chris de Loof (Belnet), Friederike Schröder-Pander (Belnet), Dale Robertson (EGI), Juliana Giroletti (TU Wien), Isabel Caetano (EOSC-A), Dario Vins (TU Wien), Miguel Rey Mazon (TU Graz)	EOSC Focus
Mark Dietrich (EGI)	EOSC Beyond
Antonio Skarmeta (Univ. Murcia)	EOSC Titan
Gorka Epelde Unanue (Vicomtech)	EOSC Raise
Dick Schaap (MARIS)	Blue Cloud
Savvas Rogotis (BDVA), Rafiqul Haque (Insight-Centre), Gabriella Laatikainen (VTT), Mariano Blaya (IDSA)	Data Spaces Support Centre

5.3.4 Participants/speakers and topics at the FAIR-IMPACT Final Workshop 2025

Participants/Speakers	Topic
Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström, NBIS - National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden Uppsala University	ELIXIR Interoperability Platform (EIP) in the EOSC context (in-depth presentation)
Gorka Epelde Unanue, Vicomtech	RAISE project
Liise Lehtsalu, RDA Europe	RDA TIGER
Simon Hodson, CODATA	CDIF update
Nick Juty, The University of Manchester	FAIR-IMPACT mappings framework
Marc Portier, Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)	FAIR-EASE and Blue-Cloud2026

	Interoperability achievements and challenges
Roksana Wilk, ACK Cyfronet AGH	EOSC Beyond: Core solutions for the federated EOSC (in-depth presentation)